

The Influence Of Image Media On Learning Outcomes Of Class Iii Students On Theme 1 Subtema 3 Animal Growth At Uptd Sd Negeri 122337 Pematangsiantar

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to determine whether there is an influence of image media on the learning outcomes of class III students in Theme 1 Subtheme 3 Animal Growth at UPTD SD Negeri 122337 Pematang Siantar, the method in this research is a quantitative experimental type method whose research design is Pre-experimental type one pretest-posttest group. Conducted in October 2023, the population of all students at UPTD SD Negeri 122337 Pematang Siantar and a sample of 30 students consisting of 11 female students and 19 male students used was purposive sampling with two research variables: dependent variable (x) in the form of learning outcomes, as well as the independent variable (y) in the form of image media . Data collection techniques are test techniques with validity tests, reliability tests, difficulty level tests, and differentiating power tests. The results of hypothesis testing using the Normality Test , and the T Test with the help of the SPSS version 26 program , based on the results of calculations with a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$ and $db = N - 1 = 30 - 1 = 29$, we obtain $t_{0.05} = 1,699$. After obtaining $t_{count} = 32.669$ and $t_{table} = 1.699$, it can be seen that $t_{count} > t_{table}$ or $32.669 > 1.699$. So it can be concluded that H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. This explanation shows that there is an influence of the image media type learning model on student learning outcomes for theme 1, subtheme 3, animal growth, class III, SD Negeri 122337 Pematang Siantar.

INTRODUCTION

In Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System Article 1 paragraph 1 states that: Education is a conscious and planned effort to create a learning atmosphere and learning process so that students actively develop their potential to have religious spiritual strength, self-control, personality, intelligence, noble morals and skills needed by himself, society, nation and state.

The learning that occurs in class III of SD Negeri 122337 Pematang Siantar in Thematic or K13 learning is still monotonous using boring learning models so that students are less active in the learning process which causes low student learning outcomes. The learning carried out currently only requires the activity of educators, so that students feel bored when learning takes place. Apart from that, students are also not used to solving problems in learning by being creative using image media. Image media in the form of images varies according to the material to be studied and is used to convey interesting messages from teachers to students. Students who have a high level of creativity will appear more active in the learning process so that students who have a low level of creativity do not understand the material provided. As a result, students who have low abilities are not interested in participating in ongoing learning, therefore an educator needs to have appropriate learning methods such as image media so that students are interested in participating in learning.

Based on interview observations conducted by research on May 26 2023 in class III of SD Negeri 122337 Pematang Siantar on theme 1 Growth and Development of Living Creatures Sub-theme 3 Animal Growth, it turns out that teachers at this school predominantly use lecture and question and answer methods and do not use media assistance. learning that can support the teaching and learning process on the material being discussed, so that in learning activities students are less active and cannot see clearly and understand the learning material easily. This is because learning only focuses on textbooks and teachers tend to dominate learning activities.

This has a big impact on student learning outcomes which are low and have not yet achieved the Minimum Completeness Criteria (KKM). Where the value of the Indonesian language subject which was completed by KKM was 30% which was not completed by 70%, the PPKN value which was completed by KKM was 21% which was not completed by 79%, the PJOK value which was completed by KKM was 81% which was not completed by 19%. From this data there are still many students unfinished learning. From this data, there are still many students who have not completed their learning.

According to Yunita Setyo Utami (2020:2) image media is a learning tool for delivering material from teachers to students which aims to make it easier for students to understand the material, remember the content of the material explained by the teacher, increase students' insight, help students' interest in participating in learning, as well as facilitating activities in the learning process.

With the existence of learning media, it is hoped that it can improve student learning outcomes and overcome learning problems that occur at UPTD SD Negeri 122337 Pematang Siantar.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The thinking framework is a conceptual framework of how theory relates to various factors that have been identified as important problems. Learning outcomes are evidence of learning so that changes occur in an individual. The learning outcomes referred to in this research are learning outcomes in theme 1 subtheme 3 learning 4 with a focus on Indonesian, PPKN and PJOK subjects. Learning outcomes are influenced by several internal and external factors. External factors come from outside the student, while internal factors are factors that come from within the student.

From the problem formulation it can be seen that there is one independent variable which is expressed as (X) and one dependent variable which is expressed as (Y). The independent variable is image media (X), and the dependent variable is student learning outcomes (Y), thus Image media related to the learning outcomes of class V UPTD students at SD Negeri 122337 Pematang Siantar

Gambar 2.2 Kerangka Konseptual

METHODS

The research used in this research uses a quantitative approach. With a *pre-Experimental Design type*. Where the researcher used a *One-group Pretest-Posttest Design*. In research, the results of the treatment will be known more accurately because you can compare the conditions before the treatment was given. (Sugiyono: 2018).

Figure 1 One-Group Pretest-Posttest Design

Information:

O_1 = pretest score

O_2 = posttest score

X = treatment given

The population in this study were all students in class III of SD Negeri 122337 Jln Haji Adamalik Pematang Siantar with a total of 30 students . This research uses a test instrument in the form of multiple choices with the aim of measuring learning outcomes. Before it is used for data collection, the data testing stage uses validity testing, reliability testing, difficulty level testing, and differentiating data testing. In data analysis, the Normality test , Homogeneity test and T test hypothesis test were used.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

The location of the school used as the research site is SD Negeri 122337 Pematang Siantar located at Jalan Haji Adam Malik No10 Kec. West Siantar, Pematang Siantar City, North Sumatra 21142, Province: North Sumatra. The current principal is Mrs. Erlinawati Damanik, S.Pd., M.Pd. This school is accredited B (good). There are 17 teachers and education staff and 175 students.

This research was conducted for 2 weeks (2 October – 14 October 2023). In this research, researchers used a pre-experimental type of research using a one group pretest-posttest design. In the research process, the researcher first gave an initial test (pretest) to students before being given treatment using learning through image media and gave a final test (posttest) after being given treatment. This research was conducted after testing the instrument. The subjects of this research were 30 students in class III elementary school for the 2023/2024 academic year, consisting of 19 male students and 11 female students. The time allocation used for each meeting is 4 x 45 minutes.

Test instrument

1. Validity test

This test is carried out by calculating r_{using} the Pearson product moment formula and then comparing the r_{table} . If the calculated $r > r_{\text{table}}$ at a significance level of 0.05 then the question is valid for use in measuring this variable, conversely if the $r_{\text{calculated}} < r_{\text{table}}$ then the question tool is invalid and not suitable for use. There are 20 questions that have valid marks, while there are 10 questions that are invalid .

2. Reliability Test

The question reliability test aims to see the accuracy of the tool in assessing what it assesses. In this case, observe how each question item is determined in assessing or testing students' abilities and knowledge. Based on the results of the reliability test with the Kr20 model, the correlation coefficient is $0.80 < r_{11} < 1.00$ so the interpretation

is included in the high value range. Then it can be concluded that the data is declared reliable.

3. Test Difficulty Level

The difficulty level test is carried out to see the level of difficulty of each question that has been distributed and determine whether the question is too easy or too difficult. Of the 30 questions tested, 7 questions were classified as easy (6, 9, 14, 16, 17, 23, 24), 20 questions were classified as medium (1, 3, 5, 7, 8, 11), 12,13,15,18,19,20,21,22,25,26,27,28,29,30) and 3 questions in the like category (2,4,10).

4. Discriminating Power Test

This test is carried out to find out whether the question items have a classification of very bad, bad, fair, good or very good distinguishing power.

Data analysis

5. Normality test

The normality test is carried out to find out whether the pretest and posttest data are normally distributed or not. To find normality of data in this study, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov formula was used. Data is said to be normal, if the significant value is > 0.05 , conversely if the significant value is < 0.05 then the data is said to be abnormal. Normality test results were carried out using SPSS version 26 with the following data:

Table 1 Normality test

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistics	df	Sig.	Statistics	Df	Sig.
PreTest	.133	30	.183	.961	30	.335
PostTest	.155	30	.062	.938	30	.082

Based on the table above in the output of the One Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test, it can be seen that the sample was 30 students. Sig (2- Tailed) shows the pretest value in the normality test, namely 0.183. Meanwhile, the posttest value for the normality test was 0.062. If the probability is > 0.05 , it means the data is said to be normal.

Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis testing was carried out to determine the positive and significant influence between image media and student learning outcomes. Hypothesis testing using a paired simple t test with the help of IBM SPSS 26 with the following results:

	Paired Differences	t	df	Sig.

		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				(2-tailed)
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	PreTest - PostTest	37,000	6,242	1,140	39,331	34,669	32,466	29	,000

To determine the price of ttable, the researcher used the t distribution with a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$ and $db = N - 1 = 30 - 1 = 29$, so we obtained $t_{0.05} = 1.699$. After obtaining $t_{count} = 32.669$ and $t_{table} = 1.699$, it can be seen that $t_{count} > t_{table}$ or $32.669 > 1.699$. So it can be concluded that H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. This explanation shows that there is an influence of the image media type learning model on student learning outcomes for theme 1 subtheme 3 animal growth class III SD Negeri 122337 Pematang Siantar.

Discussion

This research was conducted to determine the effect of image media on class III learning outcomes in theme 1 subtheme 3 animal growth work at SD Negeri 122337 Pematang Siantar. Researchers chose image media because this learning model requires students to be more active in building their knowledge by giving students the opportunity to solve a problem by discussing it with their group members. This media also emphasizes student activity in discovering the concepts being studied and educators only act as facilitators. In this research, researchers used a pre-experimental type of research using a one group pretest-posttest design.

In the research process, the researcher first gave an initial test (pretest) to students before being given treatment using learning through image media and gave a final test (posttest) after being given treatment. The students' highest score during the pretest was 60 and the lowest score was 20. Of which 30 students were still below the KKM, this was because the students did not fully understand the material, were less active during learning, and learning was still monotonous. After being given a pretest, the researcher taught using image media. The researcher first explained the learning material for theme 1, subtheme 3 "animal growth" in the fourth lesson to the students, then divided the students into several groups, each group consisting of 2 students. In this learning media there is a home group (initial group) and an expert group (new group after being given an assignment). Each group member will be given the same task. After the students get the assignment, the students will practice the movement of

the butterfly life cycle. Each group will see another group of friends. So that each group of students knows which group has the correct movement.

Learning using image media was carried out in 2 meetings. When learning takes place, students look active and enthusiastic about learning. After 2 meetings, the researcher gave a final test (posttest) to see the final results. The average posttest score was 80, where the highest score was 90 and the lowest score was 20. Based on the results of data analysis and hypothesis testing, the pretest average score was 40 and the posttest average score was 80, $t_{count} > t_{table}(32,466 > 1.699)$ so that H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, meaning that there is a significant influence of picture media learning on the learning outcomes of class III students on theme 1 subtheme 3 animal growth at SD Negeri 122337 Pematang Siantar.

After conducting research, it was seen that there were changes experienced by students, from not understanding to understanding, from being less active to being active, and there was an increase in grades. This is because the learning media is in groups and focuses on students so that students are interested in participating in learning.

CONCLUSION & RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

Based on the results of research conducted by researchers, the following conclusions can be drawn:

Pretest learning results of class III students at UPTD SD Negeri 122337 Pematang Siantar in learning theme 1 subtheme 3 "animal growth" got an average of 40 which was categorized as poor, while the *posttest learning results* got an average of 80 which was categorized as good. Based on the results of data analysis and hypothesis testing, the sig(2-tailed) t_{table} value is $(32.466 > 1.699)$ so that H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, this can be seen from the difference in the average *pretest score* and the average *posttest score* of students, where the average pretest value is 40 and the average posttest value is 80. Based on the results of the paired sample t test, the calculated t value $> t_{table}$ $(32.466 > 1.699)$ is obtained so that H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, which indicates that there is a significant influence of Image Media on the learning outcomes of class III students in Theme 1 Subtheme 3 at UPTD SD Negeri 122337 Pematang Siantar.

Recommendations

Based on the research that has been carried out, as recommendation material by considering findings in the field and theoretically, the author's suggestions are:

5.2.1. For teachers, this type of image learning media is very appropriate to use during the teaching and learning process because after research, image type media can improve student learning outcomes.

5.2.2. For schools, they must pay attention to, evaluate internal and external factors that influence student learning outcomes and work together to build superior schools and innovate in learning.

5.2.3. For other researchers, other researchers can conduct similar research on other subjects, so that broader information is obtained about learning media and factors that influence student learning outcomes .

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